

Analysis of Financial Performance on Sharia Stocks Listed In the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) During the Covid-19 Pandemic (As of September 30, 2021)

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Abstract: Financial performance is an analysis conducted to see the extent to which a company has implemented by using financial implementation rules properly and correctly. Companies must have healthy and efficient financial performance to earn profits and improve company performance. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, economic and business activities have decreased. The focus of this research is the analysis of financial performance on Islamic stocks listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index. The results of the study show that the independent variables consisting of Debt to Asset Ratio, Debt to Equity Ratio, Return on Assets, Return on Equity based on the results of data analysis using the Cross Section Approach (CSA) research method can be seen whether the financial performance is good or not by comparing the company average with the industry average. The results of this study indicate that the financial performance of most Islamic companies is not good, this happens because of the impact of the covid-19 pandemic which resulted in a decrease in sales because the decline in sales was not proportional to the operating costs and cost of goods sold.

Keywords: Stocks, Jakarta Islamic Index, Cross Section, Covid-19, Ratio.

I. INTRODUCTION

Finance is an integral part of a company. A good company's financial condition can be a strong foundation for the establishment of a company. Assessment of financial performance is one way that can be done by the management in order to fulfill its obligations to decision makers and also to achieve the goals set by the company. The assessment of the company's performance as a result of the management decision-making process is a complex issue because it involves the effectiveness of the use of capital and the efficiency of the company's activities concerning the value and security of various demands that arise against the company.

Companies must have healthy and efficient financial performance to earn profits and improve company performance. Therefore, financial performance is important for every company in business competition to maintain the continuity of the company. To assess the company's financial performance, we need relevant information related to the company's activities at a certain period of time to interested parties and one of the factors that can show how the company's performance is good or not, namely financial statement analysis. The importance of measuring the financial performance of a company can be explained by two theories, namely agency theory and signal theory.

At this time, economic and business activities around the world in general are experiencing a fairly drastic decline due to the Covid-19 pandemic, which is still ongoing. The existence of the Corona Virus pandemic event not only poses a threat to health but also to economic growth in a country. The impact of the spread of Covid-19 cannot be calculated with certainty. However, a slowdown in the economic system has been felt, especially in the industrial, tourism, trade, transportation and investment sectors. Likewise with Indonesia, the continued increase in the number of positive cases of Covid-19 also brings various kinds of effects to the stock market. (iNews.id, 2020).

In this study, researchers focus more on Islamic companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index stock exchange. The reason for choosing the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) is because the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) is one of the largest sharia-based stock indexes in Indonesia. In addition, the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) is used to increase investor confidence to invest in sharia-based stocks and provide benefits for investors in implementing Islamic sharia to invest in the stock exchange. The Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) consists of 30 sharia stocks that have been selected by the National

Sharia Council (DSN) per semester and have good financial performance. Then in this pandemic condition, financial performance decreased.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND DEVELOPMENT HYPOTHESES

Agency Theory

Agency theory is a theory that explains the relationship between capital owners, namely investors and managers. Agency theory based on contractual relationships between owners and managers is difficult to create because of conflicting interests. Agency theory makes a contractual model between two or more people, where one party is called the agent and the other party is called the principal.

Signal Theory

Signal theory explains why companies have the urge to provide financial statement information to external parties. This impetus arises because of asymmetric information between the company and external parties, where management knows the company's internal information which is relatively more abundant and faster than outside parties such as investors and creditors.

Financial Performance

If the company's performance is good, it will produce good performance as well, and vice versa. The financial performance of a company is very beneficial for various parties (stakeholders) such as investors, creditors, analysts, financial consultants, brokers, the government and the management themselves.

ROA (Return On Assets)

Return on Assets is a company showing a comparison between profit and assets or capital that generates the profit. It can be said that ROA is the ability of a company to generate profits during a certain period.

ROE (Return On Equity)

Return on Equity (ROE), this ratio is used to measure the performance of financial institution management in managing available capital to generate after-tax profits. Profit after tax is the net profit from operating activities after deducting taxes while the average total equity is the average core capital owned by financial institutions in percentage terms. ROE is used to show the company's ability to generate profits from the equity owned by the company.

DAR (Debt to Asset Ratio)

Debt to Asset Ratio is a comparison of the amount of debt with total assets owned by the company which measures the percentage of use of funds originating from creditors compared to all assets. This ratio is the percentage of funds provided by creditors to the company.

DER (Debt to Equity Ratio)

Debt to Equity Ratio is a comparison of the amount of debt with its own capital which measures the percentage of use of funds originating from creditors compared to own capital. If the results of the debt to equity ratio decrease, it will be even better because the level of small bank debt if it increases, the higher the risk due to the high level of debt financed from own capital.

Research Hypothesis

The hypotheses shown in this study are as follows: It is suspected that there will be a decline in the financial performance of sharia companies listed in the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) as of September 30, 2021, using the Cross Section Approach (CSA) during the COVID-19 outbreak in Indonesia.

Framework

III. METHODS

Types of research

This type of research is quantitative descriptive. Quantitative descriptive is a type of research that aims to describe or describe numbers that have been processed according to certain standards.

Population and Sample

The population in this study are companies listed in the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) in the first, second, and third quarters of 2021. The sampling technique used in this study is the purposive sampling method. With the following criteria:

1. Companies that publish company quarterly reports during 2021 on the company website or in www.idx.co.id.
2. Companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII).
3. Companies that do not experience losses during 2021.

Data analysis method

The analytical technique used in this study are two financial ratio analyzes, namely solvency and profitability. The stages in this study describe the data related to the research in the form of tables and then are given an explanation related to the data.

Then the analyst performs a comparative analysis of quarter 1, quarter 2, quarter 3 using the Cross-sectional Approach (CSA) approach.

Operational Definition and Measurement of Variables

Dependent Variable

Financial performance is an analysis carried out to see the extent to which a company has implemented it using financial implementation rules properly and correctly. Performance as an achievement that can be achieved by the company in a certain period that reflects the level of health of the company.

Independent Variable

Return On Assets (ROA)

Return on Assets (ROA) is one way to find out the extent of a company's ability to earn profits.

$$\text{ROA} = \frac{\text{Laba bersih setelah pajak}}{\text{Total asset}}$$

ReturnOnEquity(ROE)

ROE is an index with the aim of seeing the extent to which the ability of capital in providing benefits to shareholders of the company, both ordinary shares and preferred shares.

$$\text{ROE} = \frac{\text{Laba bersih setelah pajak}}{\text{Total equity}}$$

Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR)

Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) is a debt ratio used to measure how much the company's assets are financed by debt or how much the company's debt affects asset management.

$$\text{DAR} = \frac{\text{Total utang}}{\text{Total asset}}$$

Debt to Equity Ratio (DER)

Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) is a ratio to measure the level of debt of a company. DER describes the level of use of debt to the company's total equity.

$$\text{DER} = \frac{\text{Total utang}}{\text{Total ekuitas}}$$

IV. FIGURES AND TABLES

Research Results And Discussion

1. Debt to Equity (DER)

Table 1. Financial Performance WithDebt to Equity Ratio

DER(%)						
Company	First Quarter	Second Quarter	Third Quarter	Company Average	Industry Average	Financial performance

ACES	39.55%	49.96%	38.63%	42.71%	107.54%	Not good
ADRO	58.17%	66.54%	64.63%	63.11%		Not good
AKRA	81.24%	85.44%	94.30%	86.99%		Not good
ANTM	65.11%	62.79%	63.69%	63.86%		Not good
BRIS	261.40%	246.71%	236.59%	248.23%		Well
BRPT	145.32%	145.28%	106.43%	132.34%		Well
CPIN	33.43%	32.50%	43.69%	36.54%		Not good
ERAA	102.35%	91.35%	79.99%	91.23%		Not good
EXCL	238.64%	245.62%	246.01%	243.42%		Well
ICBP	105.04%	101.34%	103.05%	103.14%		Not good
INCO	13.28%	14.20%	13.84%	13.77%		Not good
INDF	106.98%	102.44%	107.48%	105.63%		Not good
INKP	97.38%	86.97%	86.54%	90.30%		Well
INTP	21.33%	20.18%	21.84%	21.12%		Not good
JPFA	164.94%	141.76%	135.57%	147.42%		Well
KLBF	23.01%	21.18%	21.38%	21.86%		Not good
MICA	16.41%	14.01%	15.54%	15.32%		Not good
MNCN	26.18%	22.40%	20.15%	22.91%		Not good
PGAS	148.96%	137.26%	139.22%	141.81%		Well
PTBA	39.62%	54.47%	53.12%	49.07%		Not good
PTPP	282.02%	292.38%	295.67%	290.02%		Well
PWON	49.34%	60.19%	55.84%	55.12%		Not good
SMGR	123.97%	112.30%	96.00%	109.99%		Well
TKIM	97.05%	90.64%	86.51%	91.40%		Not good
TLKM	101.60%	139.75%	107.47%	116.27%		Well
TPIA	82.77%	88.20%	56.44%	75.80%		Not good
UNTR	57.06%	58.04%	59.35%	58.15%		Not good
UNVR	229.93%	405.11%	279.93%	304.99%		Well
WIKA	268.85%	272.87%	286.59%	276.10%		Well

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Of the 29 companies that have a Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) above the industry average, 11 companies, while the remaining 18 companies have a Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) below the industry average, which means more companies are having problems with debt financing. This problem occurred due to the pandemic that emerged in March 2020, which made the company's financial performance not good and had an impact on the payment of the company's debt.

2. Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR)

Table 2. Financial Performance with Debt to Asset Ratio

DAR (%)						
Company	First Quarter	Second Quarter	Third Quarter	Company Average	Industry Average	Financial performance
ACES	28.34%	33.31%	27.87%	29.84%		Well
ADRO	58.17%	66.54%	64.63%	63.11%		Well
AKRA	44.82%	46.07%	48.53%	46.47%		Well

ANTM	39.43%	38.57%	38.91%	38.97%	22.10%	Well
BRIS	25.09%	23.29%	22.73%	23.70%		Well
BRPT	59.24%	59.23%	52.09%	56.85%		Well
CPIN	24.47%	24.53%	30.41%	26.47%		Well
ERAA	2.68%	5.37%	7.12%	5.06%		Not good
EXCL	0.52%	1.09%	1.51%	1.04%		Not good
ICBP	2.44%	3.93%	5.81%	4.06%		Not good
INCO	13.28%	14.20%	13.84%	13.77%		Not good
INDF	106.98%	102.44%	107.48%	105.63%		Well
INKP	97.38%	86.97%	86.54%	90.30%		Well
INTP	1.56%	2.57%	5.63%	3.25%		Not good
JPFA	2.86%	5.29%	5.62%	4.59%		Not good
KLBF	3.10%	6.46%	9.30%	6.29%		Not good
MICA	5.50%	9.63%	14.42%	9.85%		Not good
MNCN	2.08%	6.22%	8.82%	5.71%		Not good
PGAS	0.89%	2.90%	4.43%	2.74%		Not good
PTBA	2.55%	5.26%	13.22%	7.01%		Not good
PTPP	0.44%	0.86%	1.46%	0.92%		Not good
PWON	1.42%	2.90%	4.35%	2.89%		Not good
SMGR	1.38%	2.32%	3.70%	2.47%		Not good
TKIM	4.77%	7.27%	10.41%	7.48%		Not good
TLKM	6.63%	15.43%	21.64%	14.57%		Not good
TPIA	4.42%	8.51%	5.41%	6.11%		Not good
UNTR	5.81%	9.37%	13.57%	9.58%		Not good
UNVR	2.74%	72.03%	78.92%	51.23%		Well
WIKA	0.62%	0.81%	1.05%	0.83%		Not good

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Of the 29 companies that have a Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) above the industry average as many as 8 companies, which means that this company is able to finance long-term debt, while 21 companies have a Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) below the industry average and it can be said unable to finance long-term debt. The decrease in long-term debt financing was due to the company's poor financial performance, the number of declines in the second to third quarters occurred due to the pandemic that emerged in March 2020.

3. Return on Assets (ROA)

Table 3. Financial Performance With Return on Assets

ROA (%)						
Company	First Quarter	Second Quarter	Third Quarter	Company Average	Industry Average	Financial performance
ACES	2.17%	3.77%	4.67%	3.54%		Not good
ADRO	2.29%	3.62%	7.38%	4.43%		Not good
AKRA	2.05%	3.15%	4.02%	3.07%		Not good
ANTM	2.32%	3.71%	5.12%	3.72%		Not good

BRIS	0.31%	0.60%	0.90%	0.60%		Not good
BRPT	2.18%	3.24%	3.28%	2.90%		Not good
CPIN	4.40%	8.13%	7.64%	6.72%		Well
ERAA	2.68%	5.37%	7.12%	5.06%		Not good
EXCL	0.52%	1.09%	1.51%	1.04%		Not good
ICBP	2.44%	3.93%	5.81%	4.06%		Not good
INCO	1.44%	2.51%	5.11%	3.02%		Not good
INDF	2.05%	3.24%	4.68%	3.32%		Not good
INKP	1.60%	3.32%	4.51%	3.14%		Not good
INTP	1.28%	2.14%	4.62%	2.68%		Not good
JPFA	2.86%	5.29%	5.62%	4.59%		Not good
KLBF	3.10%	6.46%	9.43%	6.33%		Well
MICA	5.50%	9.63%	14.42%	9.85%	5.51%	Well
MNCN	2.08%	6.22%	8.82%	5.71%		Well
PGAS	0.89%	2.90%	4.43%	2.74%		Not good
PTBA	2.55%	5.26%	13.22%	7.01%		Well
PTPP	115.43%	0.22%	0.36%	38.67%		Well
PWON	0.95%	1.81%	2.79%	1.85%		Not good
SMGR	0.61%	1.09%	1.88%	1.19%		Not good
TKIM	2.42%	3.81%	5.58%	3.94%		Not good
TLKM	3.28%	6.43%	10.42%	6.71%		Well
TPIA	2.42%	4.52%	3.46%	3.47%		Not good
UNTR	3.70%	5.93%	8.52%	6.05%		Well
UNVR	7.49%	14.26%	20.80%	14.18%		Well
WIKA	0.17%	0.21%	0.27%	0.22%		Not good

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Of the 29 companies that have a Return on Assets (ROA) above the industry average, as many as 9 companies, which means that the company has assets that are used optimally so that there is an increase and financial performance becomes good, while the remaining 20 companies have a Return on Assets (ROA) below the average. Industrial average, which means the company has decreased because the company has assets that are not used optimally. The impact of the pandemic increases operational costs and cost of goods sold which is large or not proportional to the increase in company sales, so that financial performance is not good.

4. Return on Equity (ROE)

Table 4. Financial Performance With Return on Equity (ROE)

ROE (%)						
Company	First Quarter	Second Quarter	Third Quarter	Company Average	Industry Average	Financial performance
ACES	3.03%	5.65%	6.48%	5.05%		Not good

ADRO	3.62%	6.03%	12.15%	7.27%		Not good
AKRA	3.72%	5.85%	7.81%	5.79%		Not good
ANTM	3.84%	6.04%	8.38%	6.09%		Not good
BRIS	3.30%	6.40%	9.43%	6.38%		Not good
BRPT	5.36%	7.97%	6.72%	6.68%		Not good
CPIN	6.01%	10.77%	10.99%	9.26%		Well
ERAA	5.42%	10.28%	12.82%	9.51%		Well
EXCL	1.77%	3.80%	5.22%	3.60%		Not good
ICBP	5.01%	7.91%	11.81%	8.24%		Not good
INCO	1.64%	2.87%	5.82%	3.44%		Not good
INDF	4.26%	6.57%	9.71%	6.85%		Not good
INKP	3.16%	6.22%	8.42%	5.93%		Not good
INTP	1.56%	2.57%	5.63%	3.25%		Not good
JPFA	7.58%	12.79%	13.25%	11.21%		Well
KLBF	3.81%	7.83%	11.45%	7.70%		Not good
MICA	6.41%	10.98%	16.66%	11.35%	8.45%	Well
MNCN	2.62%	7.61%	10.60%	6.94%		Not good
PGAS	2.23%	6.89%	10.17%	6.43%		Not good
PTBA	3.56%	8.13%	20.24%	10.64%		Well
PTPP	0.44%	0.86%	1.46%	0.92%		Not good
PWON	1.42%	2.90%	4.35%	2.89%		Not good
SMGR	1.38%	2.32%	3.70%	2.47%		Not good
TKIM	4.77%	7.27%	10.41%	7.48%		Not good
TLKM	6.63%	15.43%	21.63%	14.56%		Well
TPIA	4.42%	8.51%	5.41%	6.11%		Not good
UNTR	5.81%	9.37%	13.57%	9.58%		Well
UNVR	24.74%	72.03%	78.92%	58.56%		Well
WIKA	0.62%	0.81%	1.05%	0.83%		Not good

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Of the 29 companies that have a Return on Equity (ROE) above the average, 8 companies have a Return On Equity (ROE) below the industry average, meaning that the company's ability is still not good at managing its own capital to earn a profit. A good ROE will bring success to the company, where it results in high stock prices and allows the company to attract new funds easily. So that in the long term it will be possible for the company to develop, create appropriate market conditions and generate greater profits, but due to the pandemic since March 2020, the company's profits have decreased which resulted in poor financial performance.

V. CONCLUSION

This study shows that the financial performance of most companies' sharia shares is not good, this happens because of the impact of the covid-19 pandemic which resulted in a decrease in sales because the decline in sales was not proportional to the operating costs and cost of goods sold.

1. Financial performance appraisal Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) above the industry average, there are 11 companies while 18 companies have Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) below the industry average.

2. Assessment of financial performance Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) above the industry average as many as 8 companies while 21 companies have a Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) below the industry average.
3. Financial performance appraisal Return on Assets (ROA) above the industry average as many as 9 companies, while 20 companies have Return on Assets (ROA) below the industry average
4. Assessment of financial performance Return on Equity (ROE) above the average of 8 companies while 21 companies have Return On Equity (ROE) below the industry average.

Limitations of Research and Suggestions

1. This study only uses 3 quartiles of financial statements in 1 year, namely in 2021. Further research can use a longer period of time.
2. For further researchers who examine the company's financial performance on shares, it is better to add a variable that is not examined in this study, namely the liquidity ratio.

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